

IDENTITY POLITICS AND INTERRELIGIOUS DIALOGUE IN POSTCOLONIAL ASIA WITH A SPECIAL FOCUS ON MALAYSIA - Part II

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Abstract: This paper explores the intersection of identity politics and interreligious dialogue in postcolonial Asia, focusing on Malaysia, where religion, ethnicity, and ethno-nationalism converge. Using postcolonialism and contextual theology, it examines how embedded power structures and state narratives shape engagement in plural societies. It highlights the Church's role as animator-mediator in fostering dialogue, solidarity, and justice, emphasizing hybridity as a cultural and theological resource. The paper proposes a reimagined dialogue that transcends exclusivist boundaries through arts, culture, and transformative encounters at the margins.

Keywords: Identity Politics, Interreligious Dialogue, Postcolonial Asia, Malaysia.

4. MALAYSIA: DIALOGUE, PLURALISM, & IDENTITY POLITICS

4.1 Formation of Malaysia and Identity Politics

While the Federation of Malaya gained independence from the British in 1957, Malaysia was formed in 1963 with the

inclusion of Sabah and Sarawak. Malaysia has long been a cultural crossroads and home to successive kingdoms, shaped by centuries of migration, traders, colonial labour systems, and religious pluralism.¹ Of Malaysia's 33 million population, locals (*Bumiputera*) comprise about 69%, Chinese 23%, Indians 6.7%, and other smaller minorities. Islam is the majority faith with 63.5% Muslims, 18.7% Buddhists, 9.1% Christians, 6.1% Hindus, 1.8% atheists, and other religious groups.² While this diversity embodies a rich cosmopolitan heritage, demographic shifts, and disproportionate allocation of religious funding³ have reinforced *Ketuanan Melayu* (Malay supremacy)⁴ and sharpened ethnic-religious divides. Studies show that uneven implementation of the New Economic Policy and political patronage have bred corruption and inefficiency.⁵ What was once a foundation for coexistence and pride of the people has

¹ Anthony Reid, *A History of Southeast Asia, Critical Crossroads* (Chichester, UK: Wiley Blackwell, 2015).

² See The Population of Malaysia, <https://open.dosm.gov.my/dashboard/population> and <https://open.dosm.gov.my/dashboard/kawasanku> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

³ Ministry of Finance, Press Citation, "Govt allocates RM1.1 billion for Islamic affairs," 13 October 2023, <https://www.mof.gov.my/portal/en/news/press-citations/gov-t-allocates-rm1-1-billion-for-islamic-affairs>. See Ministry of Finance, Press Citation, "Unity Gov't Allocates RM50 Mln For Management Of Non-Islamic Houses Of Worship," 13 October 2023, <https://www.mof.gov.my/portal/en/news/press-citations/unity-gov-t-allocates-rm50-mln-for-management-of-non-islamic-houses-of-worship> (accessed on 02.05.2025)

⁴ *Ketuanan Melayu* is a political concept that emphasizes Malay pre-eminence and power in present-day Malaysia. The Malays claim their special position and special rights owing to their history in the area and the fact that the present Malaysian state evolved from a Malay polity.

⁵ Sulochana Nair, "Fostering National Unity and Enhancing Ethnic Relations in Malaysia: The Role of Poverty Eradication Policies," in *Rethinking Ethnicity and Nation Building, Malaysia. Sri Lanka & Fiji in Comparative Perspective*, ed. Abdul Rahman Embong (Kajang, Malaysia: PSSM, 2007), 114-151. See R. Thillainathan and Kee-Cheok Cheong, "Malaysia's New Economic Policy, Growth, and Distribution: Revisiting the Debate," *Malaysian Journal of Economic Studies* 53/1 (June 2016): 51-68; Lee Hwok Aun, "Malaysia's New Economic Policy: Fifty Years of Polarization and Impasse," *Southeast Asian Studies* 11/2 (August 2022): 299-329.

become a faultline, giving rise to the crisis of identity politics that continues to shape Malaysia's social and political life.

4.2 Ethno-Religious Nationalism and the Challenge of Extremism

Since the 1980s, Malaysia has witnessed a deep intertwining of Malay supremacy and Islamization. Legal and political structures reinforce this linkage, with issues such as conversion disputes, child custody under Shariah courts, and rhetoric framing elections as “Muslim vs. non-Muslim” sharpening communal divides. This climate is further vitiated by the spread of exclusivist ideologies – described by scholars as a “perfect religion syndrome” – that discourage interfaith dialogue and encourage religious insularity.⁶ Coupled with the rise of *Salafization*,⁷ the presence of extremist networks like ISIS and Jemaah Islamiyah has fuelled radicalization, sectarianism, and growing intolerance,⁸ while state responses remain largely reactive and insufficient to uphold pluralism as a national value.

4.3 Interfaith Dialogue & the Malaysian Consultative Council

The Malaysian Consultative Council of Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, Sikhism, and Taoism (MCCBCHST), established in 1983, serves as a key platform for promoting interreligious harmony under the motto “*Many Faiths, One Nation.*” However, Islam – administered separately through the Department of Islamic Development (JAKIM) and the constitutional authority of the Sultans – is notably excluded. This reflects a broader institutional reluctance to integrate Islamic authorities into formal interfaith dialogue structures.

⁶ Mohamad Tajuddin Mohammad Rasdi, *Not the Islam I know* (Petaling Jaya: ZI Publications, 2018), 33. See <https://ilhambooks.com/not-the-islam-i-know/> for a description of the book.

⁷ The Salafi movement is a fundamentalist revival movement within Sunni Islam originating in the late 19th century and is influential in the Islamic world. The name “*Salafiyya*” is a self-designation, calling for a return to the traditions of the “pious predecessors” (*salaf*), the first three generations of Muslims.

⁸ Ahmad Fauzi Abdul Hamid, “The Extensive Salafization of Malaysian Islam,” Yusof Ishak Institute, Singapore, *Trends in Southeast Asia*, ISEAS – 2016, no. 9, https://www.iseas.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/pdfs/TRS9_16.pdf (accessed on 02.05.2025)..

Despite these limitations, the MCCBCHST continues to play a crucial role in Malaysia's religious landscape. It has consistently spoken out against religious encroachments, including the seizure of Bibles, restrictions on worship spaces, and discriminatory dress codes. Though often overlooked by officialdom, such interventions represent a form of prophetic witness, defending Malaysia's pluralistic identity and advocating for justice across faith traditions.

4.5 Luminous Witnesses of Dialogue

Amid Malaysia's often fraught religious landscape, certain individuals stand out as luminous examples of interfaith friendship and mutual respect:

i) *Abdullah Munshi*, a 19th-century Malay scholar and Muslim, studied and translated the Gospels alongside missionary Pastor William Milne. He demonstrates that one's deep faith can coexist with openness to the other.⁹

ii) *Cardinal Soter Fernandez*, Malaysia's first cardinal, was known for standing up to the oppressive ways of the authorities and was a great advocate of interreligious dialogue. His unassuming demeanour earned him friends from all walks of life.¹⁰ He praised the head of the Islamic party (PAS), Tok Guru Datuk Nik Aziz, who was also the Chief Minister of the state of Kelantan, for his simple way of life and intervention to support the delayed renovation of a Christian chapel—an act affirming the principle of religious freedom.¹¹

⁹ Abdullah bin Abdul Kadir, *The Hikayat Abdullah*, trans. A. H. Hill (Hong Kong, Singapore, and Kuala Lumpur: Oxford University Press, 1970), 106, cited in Michael S. Northcott, "Christian Muslim Relations in West Malaysia: Islam and Christianity in the Colonial Era," *The Muslim World* 81/1 (January 1991): 50. He is also known as Munshi Abdullah (1796–1854). The term *munshi* came to be used as a respected title for persons who achieved mastery over language and politics.

¹⁰ Anthony Soter Fernandez (1932–2020) was the first Malaysian cardinal and Archbishop of Kuala Lumpur from 1983 to 2003. See Terence Netto, "Cardinal Fernandez will long be remembered for subtle defiance," 29 Oct 2020, <https://www.malaysiakini.com/columns/548540> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

¹¹ See Jerome Fernandez, "The Tok Guru I knew," 15 March 2015, <https://www.heraldmalaysia.com/news/the-tok-guru-i-knew/22902/5> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

iii) *Mother Mangalam*,¹² founder of the Pure Life Society, who dedicated her life to multifaith service and education, embodying compassion across religious boundaries.

iv) *Professor Mohamad Tajuddin Rasdi*, a Muslim academic, remains a vocal advocate for civic dialogue, pluralism, and the inclusive spirit of the Constitution.¹³

These figures exemplify genuine dialogue rooted in humility, courage, and shared human dignity.

4.6 Cultural Performance as Interreligious Dialogue

Cultural performances such as *wayang kulit* in Malaysia¹⁴ and the *Barong Landung* in Bali¹⁵ reveal how art embodies hybridity and serves as a space for dialogue, reconciliation, and moral reflection. While *wayang kulit* – drawn from Hindu epics, folklore, and Islamic imagery – has been suppressed in Malaysia under Islamization,¹⁶ it remains a powerful metaphor for layered meaning and interreligious encounter. Similarly, the *Barong Landung* ritual in Bali, symbolizing Balinese and Chinese ancestries, has mediated interethnic tensions and fostered communal healing. Together, these

¹² A. Mangalam Iyer (1926–2023), known as Mother Mangalam, was a Singaporean-born Malaysian Hindu nun and human rights activist. See Merdeka Award, Past recipients, 2010, “The Late Datin Paduka Mother A Mangalam,” <https://www.merdekaaward.my/past-recipients/for-the-awards/2010/the-late-datin-paduka-mother-a-mangalam-ap-s-iyaswamy-iyer> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

¹³ See Rex Tan, “Time to redefine ‘national culture’, says academic,” 21 May 2024. <https://www.freemalaysiatoday.com/category/nation/2024/05/21/time-to-redefine-national-culture-says-academic>. See also Prof Mohd Tajuddin Mohd Ramli, “My personal tribute to the Chinese community,” 02 February 2024, <https://mysinchew.sinchew.com.my/news/20240216/mysinchew/5395850> (both document were accessed on 02.05.2025).

¹⁴ For an introduction, see Noriah Mohammed, trans. Kathy Foley, “Malaysia,” in *World Encyclopaedia of Puppetry Arts*, <https://wepa.unima.org/en/malaysia/> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

¹⁵ Volker Gottowik, “Ethnicity and Violence in Bali. And What Barong Landung Says About It,” in *Dynamics of Religion in Southeast Asia. Magic and Modernity*, ed. Volker Gottowik (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2014), 217–236.

¹⁶ Marcos Ferrarase, “Cancellation puts spotlight on Malaysia’s cultural conservatism,” 07 July 2021, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/7/7/malaysias-performers-dance-with-conservatism> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

traditions highlight how performance, myth, and ritual can resist exclusion, cultivate dialogue, and transform cultural memory into a shared ethic of coexistence.

4.7 The *Everydayness* of Dialogue

Post-conflict Indonesia offers valuable lessons for Asia. In the Maluku Islands – once torn by Muslim-Christian violence – reconciliation was not primarily theological but cultural. Local traditions such as *pela* (network of kinship), the mnemonics of folktales, and communal songs became a catalyst for rebuilding trust. As scholar Izak Lattu observes, it was cultural memory, not formal theology, that sustained the healing process.¹⁷ The indigenous cultural capital, representing a shared heritage, was utilized by Muslims and Christians to foster a sense of community and mitigate conflict. This highlights a vital truth: dialogue is most powerful when grounded in the everyday realities of life. It takes shape not in conference halls, but in kitchens, festivals, and rice fields. It lives in shared meals, simple acts of kindness, and the rhythms of ordinary life.

Lattu notes that the collective representation of a given community through art forms “makes and remakes society’s collective existence”—as the framework of collective memory “confines and binds our most intimate remembrance to each other.”¹⁸ Given this framework, collective memory is a social reality.

4.8 A Postcolonial Vision for Nation-Building

Despite achieving political independence, many postcolonial states – including Malaysia – continue to grapple with exclusionary nation-building. Minority communities remain sidelined, their stories and names often erased from official narratives and public spaces. Religion, instead of being a

¹⁷ Izak Y. M. Lattu, *Rethinking Interreligious Dialogue: Orality, Collective Memory, and Christian-Muslim Engagements in Indonesia* (Paderborn: Brill-Schoningh, 2023).

¹⁸ Emile Durkheim, *The Elementary Forms of Religious Life*, New Translation by Carol Cosman (Oxford: Oxford University, 2001), 96, quoted in Lattu, *Rethinking Interreligious Dialogue*, xxiii.

source of unity, becomes sidelined as a folkloric token or emphasized as a flashpoint for conflict. What, then, is the role of the Church? Postcolonial thought invites us to look to the margins. Malaysia's cultural hybridity, historical wounds, and shared traditions offer raw material for crafting a more reconciled future.

5. FROM WOUNDS TO WITNESS: THE CHURCH'S ROLE IN MALAYSIA'S PLURAL SOCIETY

5.1 Tasks for the Church

The Church and its leadership are invited to assume the posture of the *Dalang*¹⁹ in the *Wayang kulit*—not seeking the spotlight, but an *animator-mediator* with a subtle, hope-filled presence. This posture requires *kenosis* – the self-emptying of power, favouring humility, spiritual resilience, and solidarity – for the *Dalang* transcends the role of a mere artist. He/she is a person of endurance, harmonizing the narratives, characters, and orchestra, mediating the community, its traditions, and the spiritual dimension. And like the *keeper of traditions* in the *Barong Landung* or *pela*, to draw from the collective memory of the peoples' history, wisdom, and rituals of kinship that bring healing and togetherness.

Through *catachresis* – the creative reimagining of symbols and narratives – the Church can speak with both cultural fluency and prophetic clarity, for she is a *keeper of tradition* (cf. Mt 13:52). This is the task before the Church: to develop a public theology which is inclusive and contextual. The Church and all faiths and faith-based entities can contribute towards the transformation of local culture, reconcile fractured communities, and accompany Malaysia on its journey toward justice and peace.

5.2 Pope Francis and the Healing of Wounded Humanity

We are living through a global shift that calls for a renewed role for the Church—one rooted in healing and proximity

¹⁹ In traditional performance, the *dalang* is the central figure who sits behind the screen and animates the puppets, narrates the plot, interprets the characters, and directs the accompanying gamelan orchestra. The *dalang* functions as a mediator between the community, its cultural traditions, and the spiritual dimension.

to human suffering. Pope Francis envisions the Church as a “field hospital after battle,” tasked with the ability to heal wounds.²⁰ In documents such as *Evangelii Gaudium* (EG), *Amoris Laetitia*, and *Human Fraternity for World Peace & Living Together*, Pope Francis emphasizes that true healing requires restoring the human conscience, affirming religious values, and resisting materialistic individualism. This mission emerges from the cries of the poor, the displaced, and the excluded, where pain and hope intersect. These margins are not peripheral but foundational: they are where solidarity takes root and dialogue becomes possible.

5.3 Pluralism as Divine Will

Diversity is a divine gift: both Christian and Islamic traditions affirm that religious and cultural plurality is willed by God.²¹ In the Human Fraternity document, Pope Francis calls societies to move beyond labels like “minorities” towards “full citizenship” for all—grounded in equal dignity and shared purpose. Segregation, religious surveillance, and restricted public spaces denigrate human dignity. Dialogue, he insists, is the only path to rebuild society—and we must never grow weary of it.

5.4 Rebuilding the Fabric of Society

Pope Francis acknowledges that “to be part of a people... is a slow, difficult process” (FT 158), through the “growth of a peaceful and multifaceted culture of encounter” where every new generation is initiated into the “social memory” of being a people (EG 220). As *Fratelli Tutti* reminds, “No one is saved alone; we can only be saved together” (FT 32; cf. LG 9). A synodal Church walks with others – across boundaries

²⁰ Vatican, Interview with Pope Francis by Anthony Spadaro, 21 Sept 2013, https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2013/september/documents/papa-francesco_20130921_intervista-spadaro.html (accessed on 02.05.2025).

²¹ Pope Francis, Document on “Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together,” Abu Dhabi, 4 February 2019, https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/travels/2019/outside/documents/papa-francesco_20190204_documento-fratellanza-umana.html (accessed on 02.05.2025).

of faith, culture, and class – to listen, restore trust, and sow peace. This includes youth engagement, educational reform, and grassroots-level peace-building initiatives. In 2023, a joint Buddhist-Catholic statement called for ‘ancient wisdom’ to respond to the cries of a wounded humanity and a battered earth.²² Dialogue thus becomes both a spiritual discipline and a civic necessity.

5.5 Vatican II: A Turning Point for Dialogue

The Second Vatican Council marked a turning point in the Church’s understanding of other religions. *Nostra Aetate* affirmed that the Church “rejects nothing that is true and holy” in other faiths (NA 2), while *Lumen Gentium* and *Dignitatis Humanae* upheld freedom of conscience (LG 16, DH 3) and the openness to truth wherever it may be found. These declarations laid a firm theological foundation for interfaith friendship, expanding the vision of the “People of God” to include all who seek truth, justice, and peace.

5.6 The FABC’s Mission of Dialogue

Emerging from the crucible of Asia’s suffering and postcolonial realities, marked by cultural plurality, widespread poverty, and religious diversity, the Federation of Asian Bishops’ Conferences (FABC) envisioned a path of “triple dialogue” with the poor, with cultures, and religions of Asia—not as strategy but as “the time of the heirs” inaugurating a decisive way of being church in Asia.²³ The Bishops’ Institute for Interreligious Affairs affirms that Asia’s pluralism and diversity are not a threat, but a sign of the Spirit’s creative presence (BIRA V/2, Pattaya 1994).

²² Vatican, “Final Statement of the Dicastery for Interreligious Dialogue at the end of the Seventh Buddhist-Christian Colloquium,” Bangkok, 13–16 November 2023, <https://press.vatican.va/content/salastampa/en/bollettino/pubblico/2023/11/16/231116c.html> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

²³ See Gaudencio Rosales and Catalino Arévalo (eds.), *For All the Peoples of Asia: Federation of Asian Bishops’ Conferences Documents from 1970 to 1991*, vol. 1, FAPA I (Quezon City: Claretian Publications, 1992), xv-xxii.

Dialogue, therefore, is integral to the Church's mission of holistic liberation: economic, socio-cultural, and spiritual.

This conviction has been central to the reflections of the FABC from the beginning which recognized the Spirit's presence in Asian cultures and religions (1974), to the Spirit's role in Asian religiosity and mysticism (1990), the Spirit at work among all peoples and faiths (1999), a Christo-pneumatological mission (2004), and a humble proclamation that acknowledges the Spirit's work beyond the Church (2012).²⁴

5.6 Christology and Dialogue

At the heart of this understanding stands the Church's confession that "there is one God; there is also one mediator between God and humankind, Christ Jesus" (1 Tim 2:5). Guided by *Lumen Gentium*, no. 16 and *Nostra Aetate*, no. 2, Catholic theology recognizes that God's grace extends beyond the Church's visible boundaries and works wherever truth and goodness dwell. Thus, Christ's mediation is inclusive—the defining horizon through which Christians discern the divine at work in all peoples.

The prologue of John's Gospel reveals that the divine Word, *Logos*, has always been active in all creation and history—"In the beginning was the Word... and the Word became flesh" (Jn 1:14). The Church Father, Justin Martyr, discerned in all cultures the *semina Verbi* or "seeds of the Word" (*Ad Gentes*, nos. 1, 3). Dialogue, therefore, becomes participation in the universal manifestation of the *Logos*, who "enlightens everyone" (Jn 1:9).²⁵

In Asia's pluralistic context, dialogue complements proclamation. Christ remains the unique mediator, yet God pursues the salvation of all in mysterious ways known to him (*Gaudium et Spes*, no. 22). This outlook frees the Church

²⁴ See FABC Papers 96, *Methodology: Asian Christian Theology—Doing Theology in Asia Today* (1999); FABC Papers 81, *The Spirit at Work in Asia Today* (1998); FABC Papers 108, *Theologizing at the Service of Life* (2003).

²⁵ Justin Martyr, *First Apology*, in *The First and Second Apologies*, trans. Leslie W. Barnard (New York: Paulist Press, 1997), 46.

from triumphalism and calls for humility in recognizing the Spirit's work through other faiths. Such a vision finds resonance in theologians like Michael Amaladoss, who interprets dialogue as participation in God's saving action already at work in other religions.²⁶

5.6.1 Christology, Pneumatology, and the Asian Context

The mystery of the Incarnation grounds dialogue in the *kenosis* (self-emptying): the Son enters human history from within, modelling relational openness and solidarity. The Church, as the Body of Christ, continues this incarnational mission by engaging other faiths in humility and love. Synchronistically, the Spirit actualizes Christ's redemptive work across all times and cultures. The Spirit has often used "powerlessness and vulnerability" to effect social change.²⁷ Scripture reveals the Spirit poured out on all humanity (Acts 2:17), moving freely where it wills (Jn 3:8), and leading all into truth (Jn 16:13). The FABC repeatedly affirms that the Spirit's activity transcends ecclesial boundaries, guiding peoples, cultures, and religions toward true freedom and fullness.²⁸

A theology of dialogue in Asia must therefore hold Christology and Pneumatology in dynamic tension. Christology without Pneumatology risks exclusivism or domination; Pneumatology without Christology risks relativism or dilution.²⁹ Held together, they form a Trinitarian foundation for dialogue that is kenotic, dialogical, liberative, and mystical, transforming the wounds of history into spaces of communion and hope.

²⁶ Michael Amaladoss, *Making Harmony: Living in a Pluralist World* (New Delhi: ISPCK, 2003), 45-46.

²⁷ FABC, BIRA IV/7, 1988, art. 15.

²⁸ Peter C. Phan, *Being Religious Interreligiously: Asian Perspectives on Interfaith Dialogue* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 2004), 115-127; See also FABC BIRA IV/3, 1986, art.16.

²⁹ "If I were to draw but one conclusion from the whole of my work on the Holy Spirit, I would express it in these words: 'no Christology without pneumatology and no pneumatology without Christology.'" Yves J. M. Congar, *The Word and the Spirit* (trans. David Smith; London: Geoffrey Chapman, 1984 / San Francisco: Harper & Row, 1986), 1.

5.6.2 Postcolonial Reinterpretation

In postcolonial Asia, this Christo-Pneumatological framework acquires special significance, as Western Christological paradigms often carried colonial assumptions of superiority. Such an Asian theology resonates with postcolonial notions of hybridity and “third space,” where identities are negotiated and renewed.³⁰ The Spirit is especially active in these liminal spaces – in movements of liberation, ecological justice, cultural renewal, arts and healing – breathing life into the margins of history. In the face of various forms of neo-nationalism, identity politics, and exclusion, the Scriptures and the Risen Lord constantly remind us, “Do not be afraid... I am with you.” What was crucified on the cross is all forms of triumphalism and subjugation.

5.6.3 Toward a Fusion of Horizons

Drawing from Hans-Georg Gadamer’s concept of the “fusion of horizons,” interreligious dialogue can be understood as a transformative encounter where different insights and worldviews meet, challenge, and enrich one another. For the Asian Church, this fusion entails a deeper theological and pastoral openness: embracing the interconnectedness of poverty and religiosity as a spiritual resource rather than a limitation; recognizing religious and cultural pluralism as a space for mutual growth rather than threat; and reimagining the margins—not as empty zones of deprivation and inactivity, but as crucibles of creativity, resistance, and renewal. Genuine dialogue requires humility, trust, and recognition of vulnerability—an openness to being changed by the other while remaining rooted in one’s faith tradition.

5.7 Theologizing at the Intersections

Acknowledging that the Spirit of God is at work in all peoples and cultures, time and place, allows the Church to affirm both the universality of Christ and the operation of God’s salvific grace beyond explicit Christian confession.

³⁰ Homi K. Bhabha, *The Location of Culture* (London: Routledge, 1994), 36-39.

5.7.1 Deconstructing Binary Fixity and Centrism

Postcolonial thinkers like Homi Bhabha and Edward Said challenge rigid binaries. Malaysian life – marked by hybrid foods, festivals, and friendships – reflects this fluidity. Christ himself manifests dual qualities: fully divine, fully human. Thus, the “in-between” becomes sacred terrain. Theology too must blend these intersections, where complexity gives rise to insight and grace, as well as synthesis and harmony.

The Church must move beyond vestiges of androcentrism, clericalism, and triumphalism. As Enrique Dussel reminds us, divine election is not a privilege, but a call to responsibility.³¹ A decentred Church listens to voices from below and affirms the dignity of all, especially the poor.

5.7.2 A Prophetic Sensitivity to the Marginalized

The *locus* of theologizing must begin from the life realities and faith reflections of the people. Faith demands listening to the “magisterium of the poor.”³² In Mt 25, judgment is based not on mere affirmation of dogmas, but values of care and compassion for the least—the migrants, refugees, orphans, widows, and the earth itself.

Pope Francis urges us in the Parable of the Good Samaritan to rebuild society “by identifying with the vulnerability of others [and] reject the creation of a society of exclusion” (FT 67). Dialogue affirms the other’s full humanity and helps forge a shared *Malaysia-ness* rooted in mutual care. God’s image is most clearly seen in the faces of the poor and marginalized, the ‘*anawim*’ of God, over those who wield power and wealth. Discipleship in such contexts involves speaking against injustice, with deep relational care. All religions should resist fusion with nationalism. Instead,

³¹ Enrique Dussel, “The Epistemological Decolonization of Theology,” *Concilium Journal: Postcolonial Theology* (2013/2): 28.

³² Cf. Aloysius Pieris, *Fire and Water: Basic Issues in Asian Buddhism and Christianity* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1996), 154-157. Pieris distinguishes the “pastoral magisterium” of the bishops, the “academic magisterium” of the theologians, and “the magisterium of the people,” especially of the poor, which he identifies as the “third magisterium” of the poor.

they should stand for the common good, uphold the dignity of all citizens, and rehumanize the public square.

5.7.3 Shared Identities and Shared Destiny

Fear of difference often drives majoritarian dominance. Yet Malaysia's shared memory binds its communities in a common history of loss and endurance through colonial occupation and the war years. During the COVID-19 crisis, Malaysians, like many others, reached out to the least fortunate from various ethnic and religious communities in acts of solidarity. That compassion must become permanent, a part of the nation's value—not an isolated or crisis-driven act.

Identity is not static; it is shaped through relationships—in families, friendships, encounters, and service. Malaysia's hybridity – evident in intermarriages, multilingualism, and shared cultural spaces – is not a weakness but a strength. The Church can help cultivate these *in-between* places, where belonging is nurtured and diversity is embraced. Many older Malaysians recall *muhibbah*³³—a spirit of interracial friendship and harmony, which seems to have faded. Pope Francis calls for a “memory transfusion”³⁴ to recover these buried virtues and carry them forward. Hence, to be Malaysian – just as to be human – is an unfinished journey. It is built through stories, relationships, and acts of compassion. The Church is invited to walk alongside on this journey, helping to shape a nation founded on justice,

³³ “*Muhibah* combines the meaning of kinship and togetherness, love and affection, sympathy and empathy, respect and decorum... *Muhibah* is a spirit, a spirit of togetherness, a culture of sincere and appreciative co-existence with sensitivity towards fellow citizens and fellow beings, a kinship and a fellowship among the people of this nation, Malaysia.” Kamar Oniah Kamaruzaman, *Religion and Pluralistic Co-existence: The Muhibah Perspective: A Collection of Seminar Papers* (IIUM Press, 2010), 18. See also “Religion and the Muhibah Legacy”, <https://www.ikim.gov.my/en/religion-and-the-muhibah-legacy/> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

³⁴ Vatican, “Address of Pope Francis at the Conferral of the Charlemagne Prize,” 6 May 2016, <https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2016/may> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

compassion, and hope. For “we are bound to our peoples by a common history and a common destiny.”³⁵

5.7.4 A Pilgrim Church in a Wounded World

In the face of wounds from identity politics, policies based on vested interests, religious polarization, and postcolonial anxieties, the Church authorities must continue to prioritize presence and service over any display of power. Its vocation is to accompany—to walk humbly with all, through the complexities of life. This requires becoming a synodal Church, close to the people, empowering the People of God to listen, accompany, act compassionately, and speak prophetically in the various spheres and public spaces. Humbly, we must admit that the ordained alone will never be able to accomplish such a task.

Dialogue here is not diplomacy but discipleship. It leads the Church to its vocation: a sacrament of unity, a field hospital for the wounded, and a witness to hope. In Malaysia’s contested terrain, where diversity is a gift and a struggle, the Church’s role as *animator-mediator* is to empower voices, nurture interconnections, and promote reconciliation. By recalling the spirit of *muhibbah* (communal harmony) and building on the principles of the *Rukun Negara* (national charter),³⁶ the Church can help shape a future where being Malaysian means being hospitable, just, and whole. Dialogue thus becomes the language of the Gospel—spoken not only in words, but also in lives offered for the nation’s healing.

5.8 Baptismal Identity: A Counter-Narrative to Politics of Exclusion

Baptism constitutes the foundational identity of every Christian. It incorporates the believer into the Body of Christ and confers the dignity of becoming a child of God. Rooted

³⁵ FABC I Plenary Assembly, Taipei, 1974, art. 5.

³⁶ The *Rukun Negara*, proclaimed in 1970, and founded on the principles of Belief in God, Loyalty to the King and Country, Supremacy of the Constitution, Rule of Law, and Courtesy and Morality, aims to foster robust unity among the diverse communities. <https://www.malaysia.gov.my/portal/index> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

in Scripture – “As many of you as were baptized into Christ have clothed yourselves with Christ. There is no longer Jew or Greek... for all of you are one in Christ Jesus” (Gal 3:27-28) – baptismal identity transcends race, culture, and socio-political divisions. This vision differs from identity politics, founded on ethnicity and religion, which privileges some and subordinates others.

The Second Vatican Council highlights this transformative identity in *Lumen Gentium*, noting that through baptism all share equally in the dignity of God’s children and are called into communion and mission (LG 2). Baptism relativizes markers of exclusion – legal, cultural, or political – by grounding human worth in divine adoption rather than state recognition. Pope Francis extends this, insisting that baptism equips every Christian with a missionary vocation (EG 113-121) and orients them toward universal fraternity (FT 86-87). Baptismal identity thus undergirds the Church’s commitment to interreligious dialogue, since it calls the baptized to recognize in every human person the imprint of God’s image (FT 85).

For the Catholics in Malaysia, baptismal identity provides a counter-narrative to marginalization. It affirms that belonging is not contingent on demographics or politics but is rooted in Christ. This identity offers resilience in resisting legal minoritization and responsibility in bearing prophetic witness to a communion that embraces diversity. Thus, baptismal identity becomes a resource in Malaysia’s contested nationhood. By affirming inclusive and universal belonging, the Church and Christians can model an alternative community—rooted not in exclusionary race and religion, but in God’s reconciling love. In this sense, baptismal identity shapes Catholic self-understanding while contributing to interreligious dialogue and social transformation.

6. GENERATING A PATH FORWARD

6.1 Vision: From Identity Politics to Healing Dialogue

A major challenge before the Church in Asia, particularly in Malaysia, is to confront the polarizing forces of identity

politics through the dual lenses of postcolonial critique and a renewed, contextualized practice of interreligious dialogue. The paper has tried to trace how identity politics operate in Malaysia, explore its historical and theological foundations, and propose ways the Church can respond, drawing insight from Vatican II, the pastoral vision of Pope Francis, the Synod on Synodality, and the Asian ecclesial vision embodied by the Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences (FABC).

Across Asia and in Malaysia's multireligious, multi-ethnic society, the Church holds an opportunity to become a catalyst for healing. Drawing on deep cultural resources – storytelling, communal traditions, and celebrations – Christian communities can offer entry points for grassroots-level dialogue rooted in the lived narratives of the people. Dialogue here is not a mere intellectual exercise but an embodied practice: a theology expressed in food, festivals, and friendships, a theology from below: rooted in realities of life, and open to the Spirit. It is the Holy Spirit – moving through the margins and the peripheries, across traditions, and among ordinary people—who remains the true protagonist of dialogue and transformation.

6.2 The Locus: A Prophetic and Liminal Presence

The Church in Malaysia is called to make her home at the margins. Like the *dalang*, and the *keeper of traditions*, she need not dominate the stage but illuminate from the sidelines—animating the stories, shared values, and relationships within a wounded society. To be prophetic today is to embrace vulnerability, speak truth to power, and embody the Gospel in ordinary spaces: hospitals, classrooms, grocery stores—wherever life unfolds. Such a witness requires moving beyond institutional programmes toward ministry that flows from real relationships. It is at the peripheries, in overlooked places, that a renewed vision of a synodal Church can be born—one rooted in humility, presence, and shared humanity.

Pope Francis offers a framework for this vision in what we may call “Bergoglian Principles” (EG 222-237): “Time is greater than space”; “Reality is more important than ideas”; “The whole is greater than the parts”; and “unity prevails over conflict.” Pope Francis describes three ways of responding to conflict: looking away, embracing it to the point of self-destruction, or

the willingness to face conflict head on, to resolve it and to make it a link in the chain of a new process . . . In this way it becomes possible to build communion amid disagreement, but this can only be achieved by persons who are willing to go beyond the surface of the conflict and to see others in their deepest dignity (EG 227-228).

We must look for “a new and promising synthesis” or “reconciled diversity” that can be a point of entry and with the Spirit’s help take us forward (EG 230). In Malaysia’s polarized public sphere, these principles orient Christians’ presence toward encounter and accompaniment, helping to build a more inclusive society.

6.3 Method and Goal: Doing Theology for the Kingdom

Interreligious dialogue is not a peripheral activity or an optional add-on to theology—it is a vital method of doing theology *with* and *for* the world. Pope Francis has given a strong stimulus to undertake such a process. What is needed is “a fundamentally contextual theology that is capable of reading and interpreting the Gospel in the conditions in which men and women live daily, in different geographical, social, and cultural environments.”³⁷

It requires a serious engagement with the social sciences and historical realities that shape our contexts. It involves a critical discernment of both political and religious narratives, particularly those that marginalize or divide. Moreover, it

³⁷ Pope Francis, *Motu Proprio ‘Ad theologiam promovendam,’* on the promotion of the theology, 01 Nov 2023. See Tiziana Campisi, “Pope: Theology must interpret the Gospel for today’s world,” Vatican News, 01 Nov 2023, <https://www.vaticannews.va/en/pope/news/2023-11/pope-francis-motu-proprio-pontifical-theology-academy.html> (accessed on 02.05.2025).

demands the courage to articulate counter-narratives—stories of hope, justice, and inclusion that reflect the heart of the Gospel. As Pieris affirms, “Spirituality... is not the practical conclusion of theology, but the radical involvement with the poor and the oppressed, and is what creates theology.”³⁸

The goal of such theological work is not to secure ecclesiastical influence or cultural dominance, but to help realize the Reign of God: A Kingdom marked by compassion, justice, and care for the vulnerable. In this sense, interreligious dialogue is not only theological; it is profoundly political and pastoral. It resonates deeply with Malaysia’s own national aspirations – *muhibbah*, the *Rukun Negara*, and the dignity of all citizens – calling the Church to be a faithful partner in building a more just and inclusive society.

CONCLUSION

Malaysia, like most post-colonial Asian nations, epitomises diversity—ethnic, religious, cultural, and linguistic. To build on secure foundations, a nation must embrace diversity and reject narrow nationalism, sectarianism, and religious fundamentalism. Failing to do so can breed unrest and even violence. Malaysia needs not only better policies but also a prophetic imagination to create an inclusive nation founded on respect, compassion, and care for the vulnerable.

Christians and the Church are committed to living by the Gospel: by listening to the oppressed, witnessing, and serving as a mediator and leaven in a plural society. Where fear is weaponized to divide, she is called to cast out fear through solidarity, hope, and healing, beginning with daily acts of compassion and extending to the long, patient work of trust-building and cultural renewal. By cultivating hybrid spaces where ethnicities, faiths, and worldviews intersect, she can help nurture a new culture where faith is dialogical, theology is public, and nationhood is reimagined through the lens of solidarity and compassion.

³⁸ Aloysius Pieris, *An Asian Theology of Liberation* (Claretian: Quezon City, 1989), 82.